

EMBEDDED ELEMENT METHOD IN MESO FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING OF TEXTILE COMPOSITES: “A GALLERY”

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ABSTRACT

The prevailing method in meso-finite element modelling of fibre reinforced composites is the continuous mesh (“full”) model in which the reinforcement and the matrix are assembled and meshed as one part. There are different difficulties in the full modelling; among others, poor mesh quality and high computational cost. The paper explores an alternative – the “embedded elements” (EE) technique for meso-FEM of fibre reinforced composites. However, the EE method suffers from volume redundancy (because of coincidence of the embedded and the host meshes) and interpenetrations of the reinforcements. The current research investigates the application of contact algorithm to eliminate the interpenetration and introduces a stiffness correction in volumes. To assess the capability of the EE method, different fibre configurations are considered and compared with the full model. The results show that there is a good agreement between the full and embedded element technique in prediction of the homogenized elastic properties, stress/strain patterns and profiles, full field strain registration and damage analysis in the loaded unit cells.

1 INTRODUCTION

Meso-scale (unit cell) finite element modelling (meso-FEM) is an important research direction in the numerical simulation of the mechanical behaviour of textile composites and for the prediction of their stiffness, strength and damage properties [1-3]. Non-continuous meshing techniques present a radical solution of the meshing problems in FE models of heterogeneous materials. Fish [4] introduced the superposition method or “s-version” of the finite element mesh and applied [5] the superposition technique to hierarchical modelling of laminated composites and discontinuous stress-strain fields. Zako et.al [6-8] proposed a “M³” (M-cube) method based on the superposition technique for multi-scale modelling and applied it to a plain weave composite. They discretized the domain of analysis into three different scales: micro, meso, and macro. Each scale is meshed separately; the full finite element stiffness matrix is created as superposition of the stiffness matrices for the different scales. Stress-strain fields in the woven composite calculated using the M-cube method were validated by comparing them with results of the full model. Jiang [9] proposed the “domain superposition technique (DST)” for woven composites modelling. In the DST the reinforcement parts (tows) and matrix are meshed separately and then superimposed by applying coupling equations to produce a combined model. The displacement coupling equation is applied between the tow and matrix meshes with interpolation functions that relate the local coordinates of the tow nodes to the global solid element (matrix element). However, this direct superposition technique was investigated for a simple geometry like plain weave and only in tensile loading and for the in-plane components of the stiffness matrix. The full homogenised stiffness matrix of the composite was not investigated, the comparison

of the local stress fields was carried on only superficially and other textile structures were not studied. The present work continues comparative studies of mesh superposition methods in meso-FEM of fibre reinforced composites. We apply and study the “embedded element” (EE) feature of the widely used ABAQUS package as a mesh superposition technique. The volume redundancy and interpenetration problems were proposed techniques in [10]. Then the application of the EE method in different aspect of textile composites ranging from calculation of the homogenized stiffness properties, stress/strain fields, full field strain, and damage are compared with continuously meshed model of “full” model and experimental results.

2 EMBEDDED ELEMENT METHOD

The EE method is based on the mesh superposition concept in which the matrix (host part) and reinforcement (embedded part) are meshed separately, but superimposed onto each other. The translational degrees of the freedom (DOFs) of the embedded part are related to the translational DOFs of the host part using the weighted average functions[11-12]. The embedded element method leads to good quality mesh in the matrix and in the yarns and solves the interpenetration problem [10] by applying a contact “interaction” between the reinforcement parts[13]. The volume redundancy effect in the superimposed regions was compensated as follows[13]:

$$\mathbf{D}_{\text{emb}} = [\mathbf{D}_f] - [\mathbf{D}_m] \quad (1)$$

where D_i is the constitutive stiffness matrix for the material of the fibre “f” or matrix “m” elements. The stress components in the embedded region σ_{emb} were recalculated as:

$$\{\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\text{emb}}\} = [\mathbf{D}_{\text{emb}}] \{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{emb}}\} \quad (2)$$

To verify the EE method in meso-FE modelling of fibre reinforced composites, different models are investigated that will be discussed in the following section.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 STRESS FILEDS OUTSIDE OF THE EMBEDDED REGION[12]

Four different models are considered, covering the main features of micro- and meso-FE of fibre reinforced composites. The first three models (fibre level) are used for verification and the last one (5H satin composite) for validation of the EE technique (figure 1). The homogenized properties of the composite, stress pattern and profiles for different applied loading are compared in each case with the full model [12]. In this section, only the results of “fourth model”, 5H satin composite will be discussed.

Figure 1 Different models used for verification of the EE method, global co-ordinate systems and mesh configurations in full (F) and EE (E) methods: (a) Single UD fibre model (b) Irregularly distributed UD fibres; (c) Single crimped yarn; (d) 5H satin reinforced composite.

A 5-harness satin weave composite from Ref. [14-15] is considered as a benchmark. The unit cell dimension is $7.5 \times 7.5 \times 0.324$ mm. Different displacements in the periodic boundary condition (PBC) applied to the unit cell with average tensile strain of $\bar{\epsilon} = 0.134\%$. The global CS XYZ corresponds to the CS used in the unit cell, with X being the warp direction, and Y the warp direction (Fig.2).

Figure 2 Unit cell model and stress pattern, loading in X direction, in full (F) and embedded element (E) methods.

In Table 1, the homogenized properties calculated using EE and PBC are compared with the full method [14], and experiment [15]. PBC were applied in the full model [14] as well.

Mechanical properties	Full method (FM)[14]	Embedded element method(EEM)	Experiment (EXP)[15]	Difference (%) (EEM vs FM)	Difference (%) (EEM vs EXP)
$E_{XX}(\text{GPa})$	56.49	56.63	57 ± 1	0.25	-0.62
$E_{YY}(\text{GPa})$	56.41	56.63	-NA-	0.39	
$E_{ZZ}(\text{GPa})$	10.53	10.55	-NA-	0.15	
ν_{XY}	0.08	0.09	0.05 ± 0.02	12.5	
ν_{XZ}	0.41	0.46	-NA-	12.4	
ν_{YZ}	0.41	0.46	-NA-	12.4	
$G_{XY}(\text{GPa})$	4.28	4.77	4.17	11.4	14.2
$G_{XZ}(\text{GPa})$	3.05	3.26	-NA-	6.96	
$G_{YZ}(\text{GPa})$	3.05	3.26	-NA-	6.96	

Table 1 Homogenized properties of the 5H satin carbon/PPS composite from full and embedded element methods and experiment (PBC).

There is a reasonable agreement between the results of the EE and full methods. The maximum difference between the EE and full methods is about 12% for the Poisson’s ratios. The same tendency was observed for the irregular UD unit cell: the difference between the full and EE results is larger for Poisson’s ratios and shear moduli. However, the difference in shear moduli is below 12% and in Young’s moduli below 0.4%. The other parameter that should be investigated in the meso-models is the stress/strain fields in the unit cells. The stress/strain field is the paramount factor in damage modelling. The stress fields in warp and weft yarns are compared using the local longitudinal and transverse component of stress (S11 and S22). In figures 3, 4 the stress profiles calculated with the full method are compared with the EE method. In all stress profiles the stresses are calculated at centroid of the elements in the middle line of the yarn and the origin of X axis is the apex element of the yarn. Warp yarns are numbered with 1, 2,3,4,5 and 1* and the weft yarns with 6, 7, 8,9,10 and 6* (figure 1). The yarn #1*/1 and yarn #6*/6 are two parts of the yarns at the border of the unit cell. The profiles for different yarns, with co-ordinates shifted according to the yarns position in the weave, coincide with a good accuracy – this confirms the correct application of the periodic boundary conditions.

Figure 4 5H satin model, stress profiles in warp yarns, six profiles for different yarns in the unit cell are shown together: full model (a,d) and EE model (b,e); comparison full vs embedded methods, yarn4 (c,f)

Figure 5 5H satin model, stress profiles in weft yarns, six profiles for different yarns in the unit cell are shown together: full model (a,d) and EE model (b,e); comparison full vs embedded methods, yarn4 (c,f)

From the stress patterns and profiles, it can be seen that there is an acceptable agreement between the full and EE method. The overall trend of the profiles is similar and the maximum and minimum locations in both methods coincide. These locations are important in damage analysis of the reinforced composites, since they correspond to the most probable locations for damage initiation. The maxima of longitudinal stress in warp (loading direction) are different by about 8%, transverse stress in warp and weft differ by about 5% - this gives an estimation of probable differences between the two methods in damage initiation calculation for fibre and matrix damage.

3.2 STRESS FILEDS INSIDE THE EMBEDDED REGION [13]

To show the effectiveness of the proposed formulation [13] to solve the volume redundancy in the EE method the unit cell of Figure.6 is considered. The full and EE models are in tangential contact with zero gap between the yarns ($\delta = 0$). The unit cells are loaded in X - direction (in global coordinate system) with Dirichlet displacement boundary condition (DBC). The surfaces parallel to XZ and XY planes are considered as free surfaces without any constraint. Rigid body motions are constrained at corners. The amount of loading strain is 2.5% ($\langle \varepsilon_{xx} \rangle = 2.5\%$, $\langle \dots \rangle$ designates volume averaging). To calculate the stress profiles, the yarns are cut in half parallel to the YZ plane, and a nodal path is defined at the middle line of each cross-section along the Y - axis. The nodal paths for the warp and weft yarns are defined from A to B and C to D, respectively.

Figure 6 The boundary conditions and nodal paths in the yarns with tangential contact ($\delta = 0$): (a) Unit cell model, (b) Nodal path from A to B in the weft yarn, (c) Nodal path from C to D in the weft yarn.

The local coordinate system (*LCS*) of warp yarn (*123*) coincides with global coordinate system (*GCS*); *XYZ*. The local coordinate system of weft yarn is similar to the warp yarn that is rotated 90° around the *Y*- axis in *GCS*. Figure 7 compares the stress profiles at the *LCS* of each yarn in the full and EE methods before and after stiffness correction. As could be seen, by correcting the stiffness matrix of the embedded region, there is an acceptable agreement between the full and EE method in stress calculations.

Figure 7 Comparison of stress profiles between the full and embedded element (EE) method in tangential contact condition ($\delta=0$); with/without correction of volume redundancy; Stress profiles at the symmetry plane (parallel to *YZ* plane) and middle line of the yarns (along the *Y* axis) (a), (b), (c): Warp yarn; (d),(e), (f): Weft yarn; (a),(d) *S*₁₁, (b),(e) *S*₂₂ , (c),(f) *S*₃₃.

3.3 FULL FIELD STRAIN REGISTRATION[13]

To investigate the application of the embedded element method in meso-FEM of 3D fabrics, a woven 3D orthogonal multi-layer E-glass/epoxy composite [16] is investigated. The unit cell is initially modeled in WiseTex based on the geometrical information of the textile reinforcement. The modeled yarn volumes are imported to ABAQUS using a Python code. The geometrical unit cell model exhibits severe interpenetrations of yarns in different regions [17]. In the full model the nodes are adjusted manually to solve the interpenetrations, as described in detail in [17]. The unit cell in the EE models is created by superimposing of the yarns and matrix volumes, and applying contact algorithms of ABAQUS to release the interpenetrations.

Figure 8 (a)-(d): 3D E-glass composite: (a) Unit cell of full model; (b) Unit cell of EE model, (c) Yarns in EE model; (d) Matrix in EE model.

The strain profiles at the surface of meso- unit cells for the average strain value of 0.2% ($\langle \epsilon_{xx} \rangle = 0.2\%$) along the X direction (GCS) are compared with the full model and experimental results of [18] in Figure 9.

Figure 9 Comparison of the strain patterns and profiles between the full, embedded element and experimental results for 3D E-glass composite; Tensile loading along X-direction, $\langle \epsilon_{xx} \rangle = 0.2\%$; (a) Strain pattern in the full model, (b) Strain pattern in the EE model, (c) Strain pattern from the experiment [18] (d) Comparison of the strain profiles at the middle of the unit cells from FE (full and EE), and experiment (The path is defined from A to B).

As it is shown in, there is a good agreement between the non-continuous mesh with the applied contact algorithm and continuous mesh (full model) and experimental results both in strain fields and profiles. Moreover, the results of strain profiles for two kinds of meshes confirm the robustness of the applied method.

3.4 DAMAGE MODELLING[19]

To investigate the application of the EE method in damage modelling of textile composites, 2D plain weave E-glass composite with detailed experimental study from literature [16, 18] was used as benchmark. The composite was modeled in WiseTex based on geometrical description and imported to ABAQUS for stiffness and damage calculations (Figure 10). Here, for damage modelling, the yarn is supposed as a unidirectional flat ply laminate. The Puck criterion [20] is employed to predict the damage initiation and orientation as part of Zinoviev's type damage development algorithm, proposed by Ivanov [21]. To model the damage propagation, the damage evolution approach of Ladeveze is implemented based on the energy release rate [22]. The current formulation of the damage model uses Zinoviev's formulations, reformulated in [21], and stiffness degradation law from [23]. It is implemented in a UMAT subroutine which updates the material properties of the yarns according to the amount of damage accumulated during the FE analysis in ABAQUS. The strength properties of impregnated yarns and matrix used in damage modelling are shown in Table 2[16]. Finally, the calculated results were compared with the experimental results of [16, 18]. Figure 10 shows the WiseTex model of 2D plain weave composite. The unit cell dimension is $12.5 \times 10.26 \times 2.45$ (mm).

Figure 10 WiseTex model of 2D plain weave E-glass composite.

Strength properties (MPa)	Impregnated yarns
Longitudinal tensile strength	1725
Longitudinal compressive strength	620
Transverse tensile strength	40
Transverse compressive strength	130
Shear strength	70
Strength properties (MPa)	Matrix
Tensile strength	76
Compressive strength	118
Shear strength	88

Table 2 Strength properties of yarns and matrix used in damage modelling [23].

Figure 11 compares the stress-strain curve for damage modelling of the 2D plain weave composite from author's method, Hoffman damage criterion using SACOM [24] and experiment [16]. In SACOM software[24] continuous meshes and Hoffman's stiffness degradation was used for damage modelling. Regarding to the symmetry of the unit cell, only single layer of the unit cell was used in the damage modelling.

Figure 11 Comparison of the stress-strain curve for damage modelling of plain weave glass composites from EE (the present work), SACOM[24] and experiment[16].

As it is shown, there is a reasonable agreement between the results. The predicted E modulus at the elastic region for authors' method has 7% deviation with experiment. Both SACOM and EE results over predict the failure and strength in warp loading. In weft loading of the unit cell the FE method has better results than SACOM with 5.9% and 7.8% difference with the experimental results for failure stress and strain. Figure 12 shows the stress patterns of S11 and S22 and damage initiation parameter in the weft yarns during warp loading of the unit cell.

Figure 12 Stress patterns and damage evolution parameter in the weft yarns for warp loading of the unit cell: (a) S11, (b) S22, (c) SVD1 (Puck's criterion).

4 CONCLUSIONS

The feasibility of usage of EE method in meso-FE modelling of textile composites is confirmed after comparison with the continuous mesh solution and experimental data for different models and applications. Contacts definition and a penalty contact algorithms were successfully applied in embedded elements FE simulations for solution of yarn volumes interpenetration problem and for

maintaining stability of the solution. The concept of stiffness correction in the redundant regions was validated vs. full model. The application of EE method in prediction of the homogenized elastic properties, stress/strain patterns and profiles, full field strain registration and damage analysis looks promising.

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